

“Internal Times” and How to Second-Quantize Fields by means of Periodic Boundary Conditions

Donatello Dolce

University of Camerino, Piazza Cavour 19F, 62032 Camerino, Italy.

Abstract

With simple but rigorous arguments we prove that the ordinary second quantization of bosonic and fermionic fields is formally equivalent to constraining the elementary degrees of freedom of the classical fields to have intrinsically periodic dynamics in time. This result confirms and extends the same formal equivalence between intrinsically periodic classical dynamics and ordinary quantum dynamics proven in previous papers. In particular it has been proven for general Hamiltonian systems in terms of canonical quantization, for elementary relativistic particles also in terms of the Feynman path integral, as well as for other remarkable correspondences of both phenomenological and theoretical fundamental interest. Our research suggests a formulation of physics based on “internal times” of intrinsically cyclic nature.

I. INTRODUCTION

We know from the wave-particle duality of Quantum Mechanics (QM) that each elementary particle or elementary system in general is described by a wave-function $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$. That is a “periodic phenomenon”, as originally named by de Broglie [1], whose natural recurrence in time is fixed by the energy through the Planck constant (we adopt natural units $c = \hbar = 1$). If the system has locally varying energy $\omega(\mathbf{x})$ due to interaction, then the wave-function has locally varying frequency $f(\mathbf{x})$, and therefore the rate of the time recurrence $T(\mathbf{x})$ is locally modulated, such that

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \phi(\mathbf{x}, t + T(\mathbf{x})). \quad (1)$$

In a perturbative description of interaction, $T(\mathbf{x})$ varies point by point in causal way as much as the energy (see also undulatory mechanics and Hamilton’s opto-mechanical analogy [2]).

In past papers [3–12] we have investigated the following legitimate, simple question: what happens if the natural local recurrence in time $T(\mathbf{x})$ of the wave function $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$, that can be associated to any generic physical system, eq.(1), is reinforced as constraint to the wave function itself by means Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBCs)? Applications of PBCs along the time dimension, all in all, has been also tested for Time Crystals, [13].

The most general answer to the above question has been given in the form of mathematical theorem in the recent paper [3] by using results from Geometric Quantization [14–17], without interpretational ambiguities. Under the very general hypothesis of Hamiltonian systems, *i.e.* generic symplectic manifolds of even dimensions equipped with a non-degenerate, closed 2-form, and $U(1)$ global symmetry, the result of such PBCs imposed as constraint is a quantization formally equivalent to the canonical quantization of the system. In particular the resulting cyclic dynamics turns out to be naturally be described in a Hilbert space, the time evolution is given by the ordinary Schrödinger equation, and the PBCs play a role formally equivalent to the canonical commutation relations and to the other Dirac’s rules of canonical QM,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \phi(\mathbf{x}, t + T(\mathbf{x})) \quad \iff \quad [x^i, \hat{p}_j] = i\delta_{ij},$$

resulting that the momentum operator is $\hat{p}_i = -i\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}$, with $i, j = 1, 2, 3$.

Along the integral curves of the system the local temporal recurrence $T(\mathbf{x})$ is defined as forming vortex tubes whose circulation is invariantly equal to the Planck constant h in the extended phase-space (Stokes’ lemma and Weil integrability condition) [2], in agreement

with the de Broglie-Planck hypothesis and with causality. Notice that under the constraint of intrinsic periodicity a wave-function of defined local energy $\omega(\mathbf{x})$ becomes a vibrating string, equipped with the whole “quantized” spectrum (in general anharmonic) of vibrational modes allowed by the constraint — in analogy with the condition of intrinsic periodicity of cyclic extra-dimension of the Kaluza-Klein theory and the corresponding “quantization” of the mass spectrum.

The theorem confirms and extends to generic Hamiltonian systems the same formal equivalence independently obtained in previous works for elementary particles (single degrees of freedom) in terms of both Feynman quantization and canonical quantization, [4–12]. The same formal equivalence has also been applied to explain in an original way non-trivial quantum phenomena such as superconductivity and graphene physics [11, 12]. The ansatz has also revealed a geometrodynamical origin of gauge interaction analogous to that of gravitational interaction in General Relativity (GR), [5, 7], see par.(IV) for a short review, and a formal derivation of the AdS/CFT correspondence, [6].

In this paper we demonstrate the validity of the formal equivalence between intrinsically periodic dynamics and ordinary Quantum Field Theory (QFT) in terms of second quantization, for both bosonic and fermionic fields [18]. In the light of paper [3], the result was expected as fields are anyhow Hamiltonian systems, even if with infinite degrees of freedom (*d.o.f.*). In other words we establish a direct link between temporal PBCs and the field commutators of ordinary second quantization with arguments completely independent with respect to those used in previous demonstrations.

Intuitively the idea can be regarded as a sort of relativistic generalization to the time dimension of the semi-classical quantization of “a particle in a Box” where the quantization is achieved by imposing BCs in time rather than in space (*e.g.* consider that Lorentz boosts “mix” space and time dimensions) — notice however the quantization obtained is proven to be fully equivalent to canonical quantization for every Hamiltonian system. For some aspects, up to a Wick rotation, it can also be interpreted in analogy to the dimensional reduction of the Euclidean time in finite temperature QFT, [11, 12, 19, 20]. The correspondence between classical and quantum dynamics resulting from the intrinsic Euclidean-time periodicity in finite temperature QFT has deep similarities to that resulting from the intrinsic Minkowskian-time periodicity in ordinary QFT discussed in this paper. The same idea of dimensional reduction has been applied in [6] to infer the classical to quantum correspon-

dence at the base of the AdS/CFT correspondence [21].

The analogy between Euclidean-time periodicity and Minkowskian-time periodicity can also be used to illustrate a particular physical motivation of our ansatz, relevant to the problem of time in Quantum Gravity (QG). As argued by Rovelli in [22], statistical mechanics and equilibrium thermodynamics suggest the existence of “internal times” if applied to GR. Rovelli’s motivation for “internal times” seems here to find additional justification directly from QFT, and from QM in general [3]. The possibility of “internal times” in the context of quantum-relativistic particle physics and QM, as well as the emergence of the “thermodynamical time”, has been discussed in detail for Elementary Cycles Theory (ECT) in [3–12]. ECT is in fact explicitly built on the ansatz of “internal time coordinates” characterized by intrinsic Minkowskian periodicity (named “internal clocks” or “Elementary Cycles”) as possible origin of quantization of elementary physical systems.

The proofs of this paper, being based on the physics of the Harmonic Oscillator (HO) in flat (topologically non-trivial) space-time, are strictly applicable to non-interacting theories. However in par.(IV) we will discuss how to possibly generalize the result to interaction. Among the various possible approaches we will shortly review [5], where gauge interaction turns out to be directly inferred in terms of space-time geometrodynamics (*Principle of General Invariance*), due to the non-trivial topology of space-time in ECT. These results could contribute to a better understanding of quantization and could be useful to addressing problems related to the concept of time in the quantization of GR.

II. SECOND QUANTIZATION OF BOSONS

The quantization of the HO is at the base of the second quantization of fields and it is particularly simple to interpret in terms of intrinsic periodicity. Being an isochronous system, the HO has global periodicity T , *i.e.* the period does not vary along the integral curves.

A. Harmonic Oscillator

Consider a HO of characteristic fundamental period $T = 2\pi/\omega$ in one spatial dimension. This must be regarded a single *d.o.f.* of a Klein-Gordon (KG) field. The Hamiltonian is

$$H_{HO} = \frac{1}{2}(p^2 + \omega^2 q^2) = \frac{1}{2}\omega(a^\dagger a + aa^\dagger),$$

where a and a^\dagger parametrize the phase-space variables as usual: $q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\omega}}(a + a^\dagger)$ and $p = i\sqrt{\frac{\omega}{2}}(a^\dagger - a)$.

Before starting our proof we note that, for any arbitrary time t , the constraint of global intrinsic periodicity $q(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} q(t)$ implies that each solution $q(t)$ is a generic superposition of harmonic eigenmodes $q_n(t) = A_n \exp(-i\omega_n t)$ for some normalization constants A_n (Fourier coefficients), such that $i\partial_t q_n(t) = \omega_n q_n(t)$, with harmonic spectrum $\omega_n = n\omega$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$. So the system can be represented, at a statistical level, by a Hilbert state $|q\rangle$ defined in the infinite dimensional Hilbert space of complete orthogonal basis $|n\rangle$ associated to the harmonics $q_n(t)$. The time evolution is thus given by the Schrödinger equation $i\partial_t |q\rangle = \hat{H}_{HO} |q\rangle$, where \hat{H}_{HO} is the Hilbert operator such that $\hat{H}_{HO} |n\rangle = \omega_n |n\rangle$. Similar arguments have been used by 't Hooft for continuous periodic Cellular Automata, *e.g.* [23–25]. Evidently, this description share some analogy with the normal ordered Quantum HO (QHO) — for a non relativistic analysis we must assume $n \in \mathbb{N}$. To establish a possible formal equivalence between the two physics we must however prove that the canonical commutation relations, and in particular the commutation relations among the ladder operators \hat{a} and \hat{a}^\dagger , can also be directly inferred from the condition of intrinsic periodicity.

Let us thus impose intrinsic periodicity as constraint by means of PBCs,

$$\hat{q}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{q}(t), \quad (2)$$

to the classical solutions $\hat{q}(t)$ and generically describe such an intrinsically periodic HO in a Hilbert space with temporal evolution given by the Schrödinger equation. We prove that the canonical quantization of the HO is formally equivalent to constraining the HO to have of intrinsic periodicity in time. In particular we want to prove, in agreement with [3–12], that

$$\begin{cases} \hat{q}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{q}(t) \\ T = 2\pi/\omega \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [\hat{q}, \hat{p}]_- = i. \quad (3)$$

The demonstration starts by assuming, for the parameters \hat{a} and \hat{a}^\dagger promoted to generic Hilbert operators and keeping Weyl ordering, the most generic commutation relation

$$[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_{\pm} = \hat{a}\hat{a}^\dagger \pm \hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} = \delta, \quad (4)$$

for some constant $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$ (we do not consider here the possibility of a dependency of δ on the extended phase space coordinates)¹.

For any Hilbert operator \hat{F} associated to the intrinsically periodic HO the time evolution resulting from the Schrödinger equation is (Heisenberg representation), $\forall t, t' \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\hat{F}(t+t') = e^{i\hat{H}_{HO}t'} \hat{F}(t) e^{-i\hat{H}_{HO}t}. \quad (5)$$

This can be evaluated by using the Lie series (Baker-Campbell-Hausdorff lemma), see [28], in terms of commutation or anti-commutation relations,

$$\begin{aligned} e^{\hat{X}} \hat{Y} e^{-\hat{X}} &= \hat{Y} + [\hat{X}, \hat{Y}]_- + \frac{[\hat{X}, [\hat{X}, \hat{Y}]_-]_-}{2!} + \dots \\ &= e^{2\hat{X}} \left(\hat{Y} - [\hat{X}, \hat{Y}]_+ + \frac{[\hat{X}, [\hat{X}, \hat{Y}]_+]_+}{2!} + \dots \right), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

or by using the general identities $e^{\hat{A}} = \sum_n \frac{\hat{A}^n}{n!}$ and $(\hat{A} + \hat{B})^n = \sum_k \binom{n}{k} \hat{A}^{n-k} \hat{B}^k$.

We write $\hat{a} = a(t)$ and $a^\dagger = a^\dagger(t)$, and we study their time evolution. Since $\hat{a}(\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a})^n = (\hat{a}\hat{a}^\dagger)^n\hat{a}$ and $\hat{a}(\hat{a}\hat{a}^\dagger)^n = (\delta \mp \hat{a}\hat{a}^\dagger)^n\hat{a}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{a}(t+t') &= e^{i\hat{H}_{HO}t'} \hat{a}(t) e^{-i\hat{H}_{HO}t} = e^{i\hat{H}_{HO}t'} e^{-\frac{i}{2}\omega t'(\hat{a}\hat{a}^\dagger \mp \hat{a}\hat{a}^\dagger + \delta)} \hat{a}(t) \\ &= e^{-\frac{i}{2}\omega t'(\delta \mp \delta)} \hat{a}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and an equivalent relation for its conjugate $\hat{a}^\dagger(t)$.

We must conclude that, $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\begin{cases} \hat{a}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{a}(t) \\ T = 2\pi/\omega \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = 1. \quad (8)$$

¹ A coordinate dependent δ , or more in general a dependency on the extended phase space coordinates, could be relevant for the problem of the quantization of gravity, as manifestation of a minimal length or time at Planck scales. The possibility of such a “generalized uncertainty principle” or similar approaches is investigated in literature, see for instance [26, 27]. As long as we consider free fields ($\omega = \text{const}$) in flat space-time, under the assumption of the ordinary de Broglie-Planck relation, we can however exclude a time dependency of δ . According to our analysis a time dependent $\delta(t)$ in eq.(4) would give $\delta(t) = \delta(t+T) = 1, \forall t$, in eq.(7), so that the commutator must be again $\delta = 1$.

In fact the anti-commutation case $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_+ = \delta$ as well as the commutation $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = 0$ must be excluded since in both cases we get a trivial evolution $a(t) = \text{const}$. We can also exclude $\delta \in \mathbb{C}$ since its imaginary part would imply a damping in the solutions.

The remaining possibilities compatible with the constraint of intrinsic periodicity are $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The negative integers $\delta = -n$ imply an inversion of role between the two ladder operators with respect to the corresponding positive integers $\delta = n$.

Finally it is easy to realize that $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = 1$ is the most stringent condition allowed. The quantization obtained with commutator $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = n$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}/\{0, 1\}$ is implicit in the most general quantization $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = 1$. For instance, acting on the vacuum with such a creation operator satisfying commutation equal to generic $n \in \mathbb{N}/\{0, 1\}$ is equivalent to acting n times on the vacuum with the creation operator satisfying $[\hat{a}, \hat{a}^\dagger]_- = 1$. In the former case however only states $|n\rangle, |2n\rangle, |3n\rangle \dots$, can be created. This would also mean that the fundamental period of the harmonic system is T/n , in contradiction with the hypothesis that the HO has fundamental period T .

Our thesis eq.(3) follows directly from eq.(8). The dynamics of an ordinary QHO obtained by imposing canonical commutation relations among the phase-space operators are therefore formally equivalent, at a statistical level, to the dynamics of a corresponding classical HO constrained to have fundamental periodicity $T = 2\pi/\omega$.

The same conclusion holds for the normal ordered Hamiltonian : $H_{HO} := \omega \hat{a} \hat{a}^\dagger$. This shows that the vacuum energy $\frac{1}{2}\omega$ depends on the ordering and not only on the BCs.² By taking track of the operators ordering, the energy eigenstates and eigenvalues of the QHO can be therefore inferred directly from the condition of intrinsic periodicity, as discussed in the premise of our proof.

B. Second Quantization of Bosonic Fields

Consider now a classical KG field

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int d^3p \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int d^3p (f_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}} + f_{\mathbf{p}}^*(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger),$$

² The PBCs used in this paper must always be interpreted up to a twist factor $e^{-i\theta}$ since both bosonic and fermionic *d.o.f* typically have $U(1)$ symmetry. For instance the PBCs of the fermionic *d.o.f* can be replaced with anti-PBCs (twist $e^{-i\pi}$) and the effect on the energy spectrum is a shift of the vacuum energy similarly to that resulting from a different ordering of the operators, [3, 5, 7–12], see also the *zitterbewegung* in eq.(13).

with the corresponding Hamiltonian

$$H_{KG} = \frac{1}{2} \int d^3p \omega_{\mathbf{p}} (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}}).$$

We have infinite *d.o.f.* but each field component $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ can be regarded as an elementary relativistic HO of fundamental periodicity $T_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi/\omega_{\mathbf{p}}$, so that the formal equivalence obtained above for the HO can be generalized. The ordinary second quantization of the KG field is thus formally equivalent to the constraint of intrinsic periodicity

$$\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t + T_{\mathbf{p}}) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (9)$$

applied for each elementary HO constituting the field. Clearly, $f_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t), \forall \mathbf{p}$, form a complete set of orthogonal functions due to the PBCs. From eq.(8), $\forall \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2$, we have

$$\begin{cases} \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t + T_{\mathbf{p}}) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ T_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi/\omega_{\mathbf{p}} \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [\hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^\dagger]_- = \delta^3(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2).$$

The KG field $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ has not a well defined periodicity being the integral of all the momentum components $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$. Each component has however a well defined periodicity $T_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi/\omega_{\mathbf{p}}$. We introduce a *modular* time evolution in which each field component $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ has a different time evolution rate $t_{\mathbf{p}}$:

$$e^{i\hat{\theta}[t]} = e^{\frac{i}{2} \int d^3p \theta_{\mathbf{p}}[t] (\hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}} \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger + \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}})}, \quad (10)$$

with $\theta_{\mathbf{p}}[t] = t_{\mathbf{p}} \omega_{\mathbf{p}}, \forall \mathbf{p}$.

We denote by $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t + [T])$ the KG field in which each component $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ has evolved in time exactly of an integer number of corresponding periods $T_{\mathbf{p}}$ with respect to the initial configuration $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$. That is,

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t + [T]) = e^{i\hat{\theta}[T]} \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) e^{-i\hat{\theta}[T]},$$

where $\theta_{\mathbf{p}}[T] = T_{\mathbf{p}} \omega_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi, \forall \mathbf{p}$.

In terms of such *modular* time evolution we have

$$\begin{cases} \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t + [T]) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \theta_{\mathbf{p}}[T] = T_{\mathbf{p}} \omega_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [\hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \hat{a}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^\dagger]_- = \delta^3(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2).$$

This also means that the second quantization expressed in terms of field commutators holds if and only if each field component is constrained to assume the same configuration after an integer number of its natural cycles

$$\begin{cases} \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t + [T]) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \Phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \theta_{\mathbf{p}}[T] = T_{\mathbf{p}}\omega_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi, \forall \mathbf{p} \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t), \dot{\Phi}(\mathbf{y}, t)]_- = i\delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}).$$

Summarizing, a classical KG field $\Phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is formally equivalent to a second quantized KG field if and only if each component $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is constrained to be intrinsically periodic with respect to its natural recurrence. In a similar way we can infer the formal equivalence between second quantization and the constraint of intrinsic periodicity for vectorial fields, with all the due prescriptions of the ordinary second quantization of gauge theories, see also sec.(IV) and [3, 5].

III. SECOND QUANTIZATION OF FERMIONS

A. Fermi and Dirac oscillator

The analysis of the Fermi oscillator will allow us to easily generalize the above formal equivalence to Dirac fields. Assuming fundamental periodicity $T = 2\pi/\omega$, the Fermi oscillator is given by the following Hamiltonian

$$\hat{H}_F = \omega \hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f}.$$

We want to prove that the condition of fundamental periodicity imposed as constraint $\hat{f}(t + T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{f}(t)$ necessarily implies the canonical anti-commutators of fermionic *d.o.f.*.

Again, the condition of intrinsic periodicity guaranties that the system can be described, at a statistical level, in a Hilbert space and that its temporal evolution is given by the Schrödinger equation. Thus we promote \hat{f} and \hat{f}^\dagger to Hilbert operators and we assume generic anti-commutation

$$[\hat{f}, \hat{f}^\dagger]_+ = \delta, \tag{11}$$

with $\delta \in \mathbb{R}$.

We want to obtain the Fermi-Dirac statistics so we directly exclude the possibility of commutation relations $[\hat{f}, \hat{f}^\dagger]_- = \delta$, and we assume $\hat{f}^2 = 0$ for obvious reasons. Without

loss of generality we temporarily assume $\omega = 1$. Since $\hat{H}_F^2 = \delta \hat{H}_F$, the eigenvalues of \hat{H}_F must be $\lambda^2 = \delta \lambda$, so that $\lambda = 0$ and δ . Let us investigate the quantization resulting from the generic anti-commutation relation eq.(11). We define $|0\rangle$ such that $\hat{H}_F|0\rangle = 0$ with $\langle 0|0\rangle = 1$. Thus $|a\rangle = \hat{f}|0\rangle = 0$ as $||a\rangle|^2 = \langle 0|\hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f}|0\rangle = 0$. Also we define $|\delta\rangle = \hat{f}^\dagger|0\rangle$ such that $||\delta\rangle|^2 = \langle 0|(\delta - \hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f})|0\rangle = \delta$.

In analogy with the bosonic case, from eq.(5) and eq.(6) we find the following time evolution

$$\hat{f}(t+t') = e^{-i\omega t'(\delta - 2\hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f})} \hat{f}(t) = e^{i2\hat{H}_F t'} e^{-i\omega t \delta} \hat{f}(t).$$

Notice the *Zitterbewegung* term in this single-particle description, *e.g.* [29].

From the condition of intrinsic periodicity $\hat{f}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{f}(t)$ we immediately have $\delta \in \mathbb{N}$. In fact, $\hat{H}_F|\delta\rangle = \hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f} \hat{f}^\dagger|0\rangle = \hat{f}^\dagger(\delta - \hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f})|0\rangle = \hat{f}^\dagger \delta|0\rangle = \delta|\delta\rangle$. Thus $(\delta - 2\delta) \in \mathbb{Z}$ and finally $\delta \in \mathbb{Z}$. Similarly, $\hat{H}_F|0\rangle = 0$ and again $\delta \in \mathbb{Z}$. The choice $-\delta \in \mathbb{N}$ is physically equivalent to $\delta \in \mathbb{N}$ for the same reasons of the bosonic case.

The case $\delta = 0$ is trivial and must be excluded because it yields $\hat{f}(t) = \text{const.}$ The case $\delta = 1$ works fine. In particular $\hat{f}(t+t')|1\rangle = \exp(-i\omega t')\hat{f}(t)|1\rangle$ and $\hat{f}^\dagger(t+t')|0\rangle = \exp(+i\omega t')\hat{f}^\dagger(t)|0\rangle$. The case $\delta = n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}/\{0,1\}$ must be excluded as well. It implies $\hat{f}(t+t')|n\rangle = \exp(-in\omega t')\hat{f}(t)|n\rangle$ and $\hat{f}^\dagger(t+t')|0\rangle = \exp(+in\omega t')\hat{f}^\dagger(t)|0\rangle$. However $|n\rangle$ cannot be interpreted as n fermions in the same state due to the underlying Dirac-Fermi statistics. It must be rather interpreted as a fermion of fundamental energy $n\omega$ in its state $|1\rangle$ since no lower energetic states can be created. In other words, similarly to the bosonic case, it means that the period T of the Hamiltonian is not the fundamental period of the system. The fundamental period in this case would be $T_n = T/n$ in contradiction with our hypothesis.

The only possible choice in eq.(11) is $\delta = 1$. Thus,

$$\begin{cases} \hat{f}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{f}(t) \\ T = 2\pi/\omega \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [\hat{f}, \hat{f}^\dagger]_+ = 1.$$

The same conclusion also apply to

$$\hat{H}'_F = \frac{1}{2}\omega(\hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f} - \hat{f} \hat{f}^\dagger), \quad (12)$$

where the time evolution is now a pure *Zitterbewegung*,

$$\hat{f}(t+t') = e^{-i\omega t'(\delta - 2\hat{f}^\dagger \hat{f})} \hat{f}(t) = e^{i2\hat{H}'_F t'} \hat{f}(t), \quad (13)$$

with the same Fock space of the previous case.

In analogy to the Fermi oscillator we may consider the Dirac oscillator defined by the Hamiltonian

$$\hat{H}_D = \omega(\hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b} - \hat{d} \hat{d}^\dagger).$$

Similarly to eq.(12), the generic anti-commutation relations eq.(11) assumed separately for both \hat{b} and \hat{d} operators lead to the evolutions

$$\hat{b}(t+t') = e^{-i\omega t'(\delta - 2\hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b})} \hat{b}(t), \quad \hat{d}(t+t') = e^{-i\omega t'(\delta - 2\hat{d}^\dagger \hat{d})} \hat{d}(t).$$

The *Zitterbewegung* is disappeared in the Dirac oscillator and thus it will disappear in the Dirac field description, as noticed in literature, *e.g.* [29, 30].

By introducing the ordinary concept of Dirac vacuum and in analogy with the Fermi oscillator we obtain

$$\begin{cases} \hat{b}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{b}(t) \\ \hat{d}(t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \hat{d}(t) \\ T = 2\pi/\omega \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} [\hat{b}, \hat{b}^\dagger]_+ = 1 \\ [\hat{d}, \hat{d}^\dagger]_+ = 1, \end{cases}$$

and all the other possible anti-commutators must be equal to zero.

B. Second Quantization for Dirac fields

We want to establish the relationship between PBCs and the second quantization of Dirac fields in analogy to the previous analysis of bosonic fields.

The Dirac field can be written in the following form

$$\Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int d^3p \psi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \int d^3p \left(u_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}} + v_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \right),$$

where $u_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ and $v_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ are spinors (we suppress the spin index). The Hamiltonian is

$$H_\Psi = \int d^3p \omega_{\mathbf{p}} (\hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger \hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}} - \hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}} \hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}}^\dagger).$$

By investigating the time evolution of these ladder operators, in complete analogy with the Dirac HO, $\forall \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2$ we obtain the following formal equivalence,

$$\begin{cases} [\hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^\dagger]_+ = \delta^3(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2) \\ [\hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^\dagger]_+ = \delta^3(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \psi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t+T) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \psi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ T_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi/\omega_{\mathbf{p}}, \end{cases}$$

and all the other anti-commutators equal to zero.

In terms of the *modular* time evolution analogous to eq.(10) the above result can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t + [T]) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \theta_{\mathbf{p}}[T] = T_{\mathbf{p}}\omega_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} [\hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \hat{b}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^\dagger]_+ = \delta^3(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2) \\ [\hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}_1}, \hat{d}_{\mathbf{p}_2}^\dagger]_+ = \delta^3(\mathbf{p}_1 - \mathbf{p}_2), \end{cases}$$

and finally

$$\begin{cases} \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t + [T]) \stackrel{\text{PBCs}}{\equiv} \Psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ \theta_{\mathbf{p}}[T] = T_{\mathbf{p}}\omega_{\mathbf{p}} = 2\pi, \forall \mathbf{p} \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow [i\Psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, t), \Psi(\mathbf{y}, t)]_+ = i\delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}) .$$

The condition of intrinsic periodicity is formally equivalent to the second quantization condition also for Dirac fields.

IV. COMMENTS ABOUT INTERACTION

Even though the results of this paper are limited to non-interacting QFT, we can establish different strategies to generalize them to interaction.

As a consequence of the equivalence between intrinsic periodicity and the canonical commutation relations of second quantization proven above, the PBCs of eq.(9) can be simply regarded as a “mathematical trick” to get the canonical commutators (without postulating them). Then we can proceed exactly as in ordinary QFT, without bothering any more about the underlying intrinsic periodicity. Interactions can be anyway introduced as usual. In particular gauge interaction can be introduced by postulating gauge invariance. Having the commutation relations, quantum observables can be calculated by the ordinary perturbative description of QFT based on the ordinary Fock space and the scattering matrix. However, in this naive case one can hope that the “mathematical trick” of the intrinsic periodicity could be useful to simplify some calculation³.

A. Topological Methods

Firstly, we may notice that in finite temperature QFT the so-called “mathematical trick” of the compactification of the Euclidean time dimension shows a relationship between quan-

³ Hopefully this could happen in all those cases in which QM seems to indicate the necessity of a compact support, such as in the “regularization” of the undamped oscillating behavior of free particle wave functions at $t \rightarrow \pm\infty$ (which are not square integrable). Intrinsic periodicity could play a relevant role in the regularization of integrals in Feynman diagrams.¹²

tum dynamics and classical (statistical) dynamics similar to the one investigated in this paper in terms of the compactification of the Minkowskian time dimension [31]. In the Matsubara theory the quantization of statistical systems at finite temperature \mathcal{T} yields PBCs (or anti-periodic BCs) with period $\beta = 1/k_B\mathcal{T}$ along the Euclidean time dimension, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, as well known in literature [19].⁴ Once that interaction is introduced in the theory these analogies suggest that topological methods similar to the perturbative ones used in finite temperature QFT and similar non trivial topological models could bring new insights about the renormalization of Feynman diagrams in ordinary QFT, see for instance [32].

B. Adaptive Perturbation Method

As a second approach, we may introduce interactions by using the anharmonic oscillator in place of the HO of the free case, and try to describe the theory in a non-perturbative way along the line proposed in [33–35]. In such “adaptive perturbation method” the interacting field acting on the vacuum follows a plane wave solution so that it makes in principle possible to extend the result of this paper to interactions.

C. General Covariance Method and Gauge Interaction

The third method that we propose consists in taking seriously the possibility of intrinsically periodic “internal time coordinates” as fundamental principle at the base of QM. This leads us to the geometrodynamical description of interaction obtained in ECT, mainly reported in [5] and shortly reviewed here.

We must introduce a covariant formalism by considering that the condition of intrinsic time periodicity eq.(9) induces through the Equations of Motion (EoM) an intrinsic spatial periodicity to the classical KG free field component

$$\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t + T_{\mathbf{p}}) = \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x} + \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}, t).$$

Of course $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}}$ are the ordinary de Broglie wavelengths: $\lambda^i p_i = 2\pi$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. Together with the time periodicity, they form a contravariant four-vector $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^\mu = \{T_{\mathbf{p}}, \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}\}$. In the

⁴ These are common PBCs for all the thermal fields modes as they all have the same temperature, contrarily to the PBCs considered here, which must be imposed by means of the *modular* time operator.

free case this is a global space-time periodicity as it is determined by the constant energy-momentum four-vector $p_\mu = \{\omega, -\mathbf{p}\}$ of the non-interacting field component $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x)$.

Thus, the condition of intrinsic periodicity eq.(9) can be equivalently introduced by requiring that $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ must be the classical solution of the following compact space-time action

$$\mathcal{S} = \oint_{X^\mu}^{X^\mu + \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^\mu} d^4x \mathcal{L}(\partial_\mu \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x), \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x)) , \quad (14)$$

where \mathcal{L} is the free KG Lagrangian density. The integral symbol $\oint_{X^\mu}^{X^\mu + \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^\mu}$ simply means that PBCs are understood at the boundary of the compact space-time. The global compactification lengths of the action select the solution $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x)$ among all the solutions of the KG EoMs and the PBCs constrain the solution $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x)$ to have global intrinsic periodicity eq.(9), defined in each space-time point $x = X$. The intrinsically periodic solution $\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x)$ of the above action is automatically second quantized according to the main result of this paper. Eq.(14) describes the intrinsically periodic HO associated to the single *d.o.f.* of the free KG field used so far to investigate second quantization.

We can now introduce interaction in terms of space-time geometrodynamics. We proceed in analogy to GR, see [5] for full details (for the sake of simplicity we will adopt the linear approximation). The globally constant four-momentum p_μ of the free case must be replaced with a locally varying four-momentum $p'_\mu(x)$ if we switch on interaction. Since this locally fixes, through the de Broglie-Planck relation, the space-time recurrence of the wave function, we must replace the global space-time recurrence $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^\mu$ of the free case with a corresponding, contravariant local four-vector $\Lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^\mu(x)$.

The compact space-time dimensions of eq.(14) suggests us that the local modulation of space-time recurrences associated to interaction can be obtained by locally “deforming” the compactification lengths of the action, that is, by locally transforming the underlying Minkowskian space-time coordinates (we are deforming the HO of the free case into a corresponding anharmonic oscillator).

In order to introduce interaction we thus perform a generic *local* transformation of coordinates

$$dx^\mu \xrightarrow{\text{interaction}} dx'^\mu(x) = dx^a e_a{}^\mu(x) ,$$

in terms of the *vierbein* $e_a{}^\mu(x)$, where $x = X$ is the generic interaction point in the locally flat background space-time. This, consistently with the resulting *local* transformation of the

compact space-time boundary, yields a generic *local* modulation of space-time recurrence,

$$\lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^{\mu} \xrightarrow{\text{interaction}} \Lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^{\mu}(X) = \int_{X^{\mu}}^{X^{\mu} + \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^{\mu}} dx^a e_a^{\mu}(x),$$

in the solution.⁵ In turn it implies a *local* modulation in the phase of the field solution, that is the generic *local* variation of four-momentum,

$$p_{\mu} \xrightarrow{\text{interaction}} p'_{\mu}(X) = e^a_{\mu}(X) p_a,$$

that we wanted to achieve in order to describe interaction. We have introduced interaction by *locally* transforming the Minkowskian space-time (flat) metric of the free case $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ into a locally “deformed” space-time, similarly to GR:

$$\eta_{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{\text{interaction}} g_{\mu\nu}(x) = e^a_{\mu}(x) e_{\nu}^b(x) \eta_{ab}.$$

Under this local transformation of space-time coordinates the original action eq.(14) is transformed into the action with locally varying boundary eq.(15) below. The rate of the recurrences varies in a local and retarded way as much as the locally varying four-momentum, during interaction. This allows us to see that our description preserves relativistic locality and causality, despite the underlying cyclic nature of space-time introduced in eq.(14). Notice that interaction is now encoded in the dynamics of the boundary in a sort of *holographic* description, [5, 6].

Two types of space-time geometrodynamics are possible: one will yield gravitational interaction as usual; the other, possible exclusively due to the non trivial topology of the model [5–7], turns out to be identified with ordinary gauge interaction.

1. Gravitational Interaction

In the first case we consider the familiar local transformations leading to *curved* space-time. Of course this describes gravitational interaction exactly as in ordinary GR. For instance, it reproduces the ordinary *clock* rate modulations and *ruler* contractions encoded in a Schwarzschild metric or other GR problems, [36]. Due to the PBCs, the locally modulated

⁵ It is useful to define the related *tangent* four-vector $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^{\mu}(x) = \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^a e_a^{\mu}(x)$ such that $p'_{\mu}(x) \lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^{\mu}(x) \equiv 2\pi, \forall x$. It is the local space-time periodicity (the “inverse” of the local four-frequency, transforming as dx^{μ}). It can be approximated to the local space-time recurrence (the one appearing in the PBCs, transforming as x^{μ}) in the weak interaction limit: $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^{\mu}(x) \sim \Lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^{\mu}(x)$. In the free case $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^{\mu} \equiv \Lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^{\mu}$, [5].

solution of the transformed action resulting from eq.(14), see also eq.(15) below, is implicitly second quantized according to the main result of this paper. We therefore understand that this approach could be relevant to the problem of the quantization of gravity.

2. Gauge Interaction

The second type of transformations reveals an inedited geometrodynamical origin of gauge interaction, as reported in [5–7] (see also original Weyl’s proposal). This is exclusively possible because the condition of intrinsic periodicity, written in terms of PBCs on a compact space-time, introduces a non-trivial topology. Any naturally occurring vector bundle, such as the tangent bundle, and other possible ones, must now come equipped with connections when anything related to them is varied. The resulting gauge invariance in the theory plays a central role in the proof of the equivalence between intrinsically periodic dynamics and canonical quantization for general Hamiltonian systems [3].

To obtain gauge interaction let us consider local transformations of the space-time whose only effect is a local “rotation” of the action space-time boundary while the metric is kept flat (local isometry)⁶

$$\sqrt{-g(x)} = 1.$$

We know that these kind of transformations have no effects on ordinary QFT, where gauge interaction is in fact introduced by postulating gauge invariance — due to its trivial topology. However, due to the compact nature of space-time in ECT, such local “rotations” of the boundary clearly imply, through the PBCs, local variations of space-time recurrence $\Lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^\mu(x)$ in the locally modulated solution $\tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(X)$ of the transformed action, see eq.(15) below. In turns this implies corresponding local variations of four-momentum $p'_\mu(x)$ in the solution, that is to say interaction, despite the flat metric. In [5], we have proven that, in the case of local isometries “rotating” the space-time boundary, this yields ordinary gauge interaction (without postulating gauge invariance).

To verify this, let us consider the simple case of a local $U(1)$ “rotation” of space-time boundary in eq.(14), as induced by the following local infinitesimal isometry,

$$e^a{}_\mu(x) = \delta^a{}_\mu - e\xi^a{}_\mu(x),$$

⁶ For the sake of simplicity, here we neglect the possibility of a local scaling factor, [5–7].

where $\xi^a{}_\mu(x)$ are associated to peculiar Killing vector fields of the $U(1)$ isometry, see eq.(15). The resulting local variation of four-momentum in the solution can be written in the form of a minimal substitution

$$p_\mu \xrightarrow{U(1) \text{ isometry}} p'_\mu(x) = p_\mu - eA_\mu(x),$$

where e and

$$A_\mu(x) = \xi^a{}_\mu(x)p_a,$$

will be in a moment identified with the electric charge and the ordinary gauge field, respectively.

Let us investigate more in detail how the solution of the action eq.(14) is transformed under this isometry. For instance we may consider the transformation of a single frequency component,

$$\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x) = e^{-ip_\mu x^\mu} \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(0),$$

(such as the fundamental harmonic mode of the intrinsically periodic solution):

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(X) \xrightarrow{U(1) \text{ isometry}} \tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(X) &= e^{-i \int_0^{X^\mu} p'_\mu(x) dx^\mu} \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(0) \\ &= V(X) \phi_{\mathbf{p}}(X), \end{aligned}$$

where the parallel transport,

$$V(X) = e^{ie \int_0^{X^\mu} A_\mu(x) dx^\mu},$$

describing the internal transformation under the isometry is formally the Wilson line of a gauge connection.

It can be used to equivalently write the locally modulated solution $\tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(x)$ of the action of locally varying compactification four-length $\Lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^\mu(x)$, see eq.(15), as the solution of the action of globally fixed compactification four-length $\lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^\mu$ and gauged KG Lagrangian density. In fact, we can substitute,

$$\phi_{\mathbf{p}}(x) = V^{-1}(x) \tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(x),$$

directly into the action eq.(14), so that,

$$\mathcal{S} = \oint_{X^\mu}^{X^\mu + \Lambda_{\mathbf{p}'}^\mu(X)} d^4x \sqrt{-g(x)} \mathcal{L} \left(e_a{}^\mu(x) \partial_\mu \tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(x), \tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(x) \right) \quad (15)$$

$$= \oint_{X^\mu}^{X^\mu + \lambda_{\mathbf{p}}^\mu} d^4x \mathcal{L} \left(V^{-1}(x) D_\mu \tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(x), V^{-1}(x) \tilde{\phi}_{\mathbf{p}'}(x) \right), \quad (16)$$

where the covariant derivative is

$$D_\mu = \partial_\mu - ieA_\mu(x).$$

Without postulating gauge invariance we have obtained the gauged KG theory as a consequence of local $U(1)$ isometries of the (topologically non-trivial) space-time coordinates of ECT, in agreement with the *Principle of General Covariance* (extended to gauge interaction, *i.e.* theory with non-trivial space-time geometry). See [5] for more details about the correspondence with ordinary gauge interaction such as gauge invariance, the kinematic term of the gauge field and the Noether currents.

Since the global PBCs of the above actions implicitly second quantize the solution, we expect that the theory automatically describes (bosonic) QED. Actually, in [5] we have also proven that the intrinsically periodic solution of the above action is formally solution of the ordinary Feynman path integral of (bosonic) QED, in full confirmation of the general correspondence between intrinsically cyclic dynamics and quantum dynamics investigated in this paper and in the previous ones [3–12].

V. CONCLUSIONS

The constraint of intrinsic time periodicity can be formally used in place of the canonical commutators in the second quantization for both bosonic and fermionic fields — in analogy with the “quantization” of the mass spectrum in the Kaluza-Klein theory where the intrinsic periodicity is on the cyclic extra-dimension. This study lays the ground of a new mathematical method potentially applicable in calculating all quantum observables in QFT, such as in Feynman diagrams, and is essentially based on the physics of classical-relativistic harmonic systems. The result can also be relevant to address the problem of time in the quantization of gravity, on the line of Rovelli’s proposal [22].

Even though the constraint of intrinsic periodicity can be safely used as a simple “mathematical trick” to quantize fields, we believe that its origin has strong physical motivations in a renewed formulation of the concept of relativistic time in terms of “internal times” of

intrinsically cyclic nature.

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